

Virtual Mouse Using Hand Gesture Recognition

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ABSTRACT: The discussion centers on the progress of gesture-based interface technologies, leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision. It explores the development of a virtual mouse system driven by AI, enabling mouse movements via gestures without the need for additional hardware. The integration of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Media Pipe in Python highlights the accessibility and potential of this innovation. Additionally, the utilization of computer vision, particularly through OpenCV, is emphasized in a tool that tracks objects through webcam data. This tool allows users to draw and manipulate a computer cursor through hand gestures, showcasing the versatility and potential of gesture-based systems. The significance of gesture recognition in enhancing human-computer interaction is apparent, as it opens up possibilities for applications like motion- to-text converters. Overall, the focus on leveraging gesture recognition and computer vision for practical applications indicates a burgeoning frontier in technology, with the aim of revolutionizing how humans interact with and control technology.

Keywords: CNN (Convolution Neural Networks), Deep learning, SVM (Support Vector Machine), KNN (K-Nearest Neighbor), ABCD (Asymmetry, Border, Color, Diameter), SVM (Support Vector Machine), Dermoscopic, Pre-processing, Feature Extraction, Segmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The narrative explores the evolution of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), specifically focusing on advancements in gesture recognition technologies. It highlights the intuitive nature of hand gestures as a mode of communication and their potential in controlling various computer functions. The discussion emphasizes the use of cameras as the primary input devices for systems utilizing gesture recognition. In the context of educational settings, the text proposes a new paradigm for HCI, leveraging the simplicity and familiarity of hand gestures for communication and interaction. It suggests a procedural approach involving the use of low-cost USB webcams for input.. The text proposes representing alphabets through hand movements as a more accessible alternative to keyboard typing for these demographics. It advocates for

gesture recognition systems as a transformative evolution in HCI, surpassing touch pads for more effective and intuitive device interaction. Furthermore, the narrative gesture and speech recognition systems as a subset of recognition technology, aiming to facilitate "touch-less typing" and foster natural and intuitive interactions with computers. The core objective is to simplify computer operations through gesture interactions. Additionally, the text discusses speech recognition as an alternative method for interacting with computers, outlining its capabilities in identifying spoken words and phrases as an alternative to traditional textual input methods like keyboards. Overall, the text provides a comprehensive overview of HCI's evolution, highlighting the potential of gesture and speech recognition technologies to redefine human-computer interactions, especially in simplifying tasks for novices and elderly users.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- 1. Hand Gesture Based Virtual Blackboard using webcam:** This application functions as a virtual board, enabling users to write numbers and letters using hand gestures, thus facilitating online interaction without requiring additional hardware input devices. The system operates by detecting user gestures through image processing, wherein the camera input is transformed into the HSV color space to identify skin and eliminate the background. Developed using OpenCV and PyTorch, the application showcases encouraging functionality.
However, there are certain limitations:
 - It reports an accuracy level of 90.125%.
 - Challenges persist in accurately discerning multiple hands or objects, potentially affecting its performance.
- 2. A Flexible Finger-mounted Airbrush Model for Immersive Freehand Painting:** They presented a project centered on a Flexible Finger-mounted Airbrush Model crafted for immersive freehand painting experiences. Their system innovatively utilizes a flexible airbrush model, harnessing the hand-tracking abilities of the Leap Motion Controller. As users use their hands across consistently captures their hand movements, extracting a range of control signals that correspond to various gestures. This virtual airbrush mirrors hand movements, adjusting its properties based on these gestures.
However, certain drawbacks have been identified:
 - The abundance of available tools might overwhelm users, potentially leading to challenges in tool selection and configuration.

3. **Air Canvas Application Using Open CV and Numpy in Python:** Their primary focus lies in the captivating and challenging domain of "air writing". This innovation seeks to improve human-machine interaction across diverse applications. Through computer vision, the system monitors finger movements in the air, translating them into text suitable for messaging or emailing. Nevertheless, the project encounters specific limitations:
 - Discerning objects, such as fingers, solely from RGB images, presents a significant challenge.
 - Implementing transitions between system states requires meticulous code management and maintenance.
4. **Virtual Mouse Control Using Colored Finger tips and Hand Gesture Recognition:** Their system is designed to recognize English characters written in the air and convert them into displayed text. It utilizes a webcam to capture finger movements equipped with LEDs, identifying patterns among the available characters. Upon identification, these characters are assumed to be valid English, and it is assumed that there are no red-colored objects, apart from the LED light, within the webcam's range. The primary objective of the system is to efficiently convert finger movements depicting English alphabets into editable text within a text editor, thereby streamlining Human- Computer Interaction. Nonetheless, it encounters specific challenges:
 - The complexity and varied nature of unidentifiable handwriting complicate the conversion of air-written text.
5. **An Economical Air Writing System Converting Finger Movements to text using web camera:** The objective of this framework is to supplant traditional pointing devices by interpreting hand gestures. It entails vision-based signal recognition, tracking, and motion analysis. Initially, the system utilizes background subtraction to separate the hand from the background and subsequently isolates fingers for identification purposes. A conventional classifier is utilized to forecast hand gesture names. Evaluations carried out on a dataset consisting of 1300 images demonstrate the method's robustness and efficiency, surpassing other state-of-the-art techniques when tested on a different dataset of hand gestures.
6. **Design and Development of Hand Gesture based virtual mouse:** Their project centers on the Design and Development of a Hand Gesture-Based Virtual Mouse. The primary goal is to enable mouse control exclusively through a basic webcam, eliminating the need for conventional hardware devices. This Virtual Mouse serves as an intermediary between users and machines, utilizing only a webcam to facilitate system interaction and handle mouse functions. Implemented using Python programming in conjunction with the OpenCV Computer Vision library, it shows promise as a, affecting its ability to fully replace traditional mice, especially in environments with insufficient lighting. An important limitation emphasized is:

- Challenges may arise when defects are detected within the operational area of the webcam. Measures have been implemented to minimize dependence on specific constraints for user hand gestures, with the goal of improving the system's adaptability

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK (CNN)

1. Image pre-processing:

Image pre-processing involves preparing the input images for the neural network by resizing them to a uniform size, normalizing pixel values, and potentially removing noise or unwanted elements. For skin lesion classification, this could include actions like standardizing lighting conditions and enhancing contrast to improve the clarity of the lesion.

2. Feature Extraction:

Feature extraction is the next step, where the CNN learns to discern meaningful patterns from the pre-processed images. This is achieved through convolutional layers that apply filters to detect edges, textures, and shapes, followed by activation functions like ReLU and often pooling layers to reduce dimensions and highlight key features.

Subsequently, the output of the convolutional layers is flattened and passed through fully connected layers, which combine the extracted features to predict the class of the input image, such as normal skin or lesion.

Overall, CNNs automatically learn to identify relevant features and classify images by prioritizing distinguishing characteristics, making them effective for tasks like image recognition and classification.

Fig: CNN Classification

IV.DATASETS

We are using MediaPipe which is **Pre-trained**, ready-to-run **models** for use with each solution. Utilizing MediaPipe's pre-trained models, we can seamlessly integrate ready-to-use solutions into our applications, negating the need for building and training on datasets. With MediaPipe's Hand Landmark task, detecting landmarks on hands in images becomes straightforward. This approach offers quick deployment and customization across various platforms, catering to diverse project needs without the overhead of dataset preparation and training.. So there is no need of the dataset.

V.METHODOLOGY

The envisioned AI-driven virtual mouse system utilizes camera image data from a personal computer or laptop. It utilizes OpenCV, a Python computer vision package, to create a video capture object that triggers the webcam to begin recording. Frames captured by the webcam are then directed to an artificial intelligence system running on the computer.

1.Hand Video Stream: Controls camera operations using Digicam, a component sourced from OpenCV. This element captures the video stream, sets the pixel dimensions (height and width) for the obtained frame, and incorporates image flipping.

2. Hand Gesture: Hand gestures and finger positions are mapped to numeric values, such as assigning 0 for a fist, 1 for the pinky finger, and so forth.

- Specific gestures like 'v_gest', 'two_finger_closed', 'pinch_major', and 'pinch_minor' are defined based on configurations of fingers or hand positions.
- The current state of each finger is determined by assessing distances between fingertip, middle knuckle, and base knuckle, with 'finger' set to 1 for an open finger and 0 otherwise.
- Each segment of a finger is allocated specific points using coordinates.
- Using Euclidean distance calculations, the state of each finger is determined based on these points and their ratios.
- These instructions appear to outline a method for analyzing hand gestures or finger positions by assessing distances and ratios between particular hand points, likely for purposes such as gesture recognition or hand tracking.
- $d = \sqrt{[(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2]}$

3.To Control Position of Pointer:

- Using Python's Mediapipe package, when either the index finger (identified as tip Id = 8) or the middle finger (tip Id = 4) is raised, it moves the computer's mouse cursor within the window.
- Detected and tracked hands are represented by sets of 21 landmarks. These landmarks' x and y coordinates are scaled between [0.0, 1.0], denoting hand positions based on the image's dimensions. The z-coordinate indicates depth, starting from the wrist. A lower z- value means the landmark is closer to the camera, and its magnitude is similar to the x-coordinate.
- The data includes detected hands, each with 21 landmarks in global coordinates. Landmark positions are represented as real-world three-dimensional x, y, and z coordinates in meters, using the hand's approximate center as the reference point.
- Handedness data indicates whether a detected hand is left or right. Each hand has a score and label. The label field contains "Left" or "Right" as strings, signifying the hand's classification. The score indicates the probability of the identified handedness, always equal to or greater than 0.5 (with the opposite handedness having an estimated probability of 1 - score).

4.To Control Mouse Function with Gestures:

To implement gesture-based interactions in a graphical interface using PyAutoGUI: Utilize libraries like MediaPipe or OpenCV to detect hands in the video feed. Identify pinch gestures on both major and minor hands, assessing their intensity based on distance and position. Assign actions to these gestures: Adjust system brightness/volume by interpreting pinch gestures on the major hand's x/y-axis with PyAutoGUI. Enable horizontal/vertical scrolling with PyAutoGUI for pinch gestures on the minor hand. Combine gesture recognition algorithms with PyAutoGUI commands to execute these actions based on detected hand gestures and finger configurations. This method facilitates interaction with the operating system and the execution of mouse functions in response to recognized gestures.

FIG: Workflow

5.Basic CNN Architecture:

Artificial intelligence has seen a significant increase in its ability to bridge the gap between people and machines. It is also greatly influenced by image recognition or image processing. Convolutional neural networks are a type of neural network. A deep learning algorithm that scans photos based on learnable weights and sizes. The visual cortex influenced the connection of neurons in human brains. CNN aids in the advanced treatment of a variety of diseases through image processing. COVnets, or Convolutional neural networks, are a type of neural network.

Fig : CNN Architecture

VI.RESULTS

An image of the user's hands and the lines that control the cursor will appear on the user's screen when the command `cv2.imshow("Webcam," img)` is used. It isn't enough to only display a camera input window; the user is also given the option to see other relevant information in the background, such as other light sources

Test Case_ID	Pre Condition	Post Condition	Output
TC-1	Invoking the camera and check whether we are able to capture livevideo.	Camera detected andlive video capturing.	Pass
TC-2	Camera detecting the Hand detected.	Hand Detected	Pass
TC-3	Detection of multipleMultiple hands hands.	Multiple Hands Detected.	Pass
TC-4	Moment of Cursor.	Cursor moves.	Pass

PREDICTED OUTPUT

VII.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper aims to implement a Virtual Control System, which focuses on cursor functions, keyboard operations, writing, and voice-to-text conversion. Hand gestures serve as the primary interaction method, eliminating the necessity for a mouse and keyboard, thus reducing hardware costs. The system is designed to operate with a basic webcam for gesture recognition.

The system's applications extend to education, particularly in smart classrooms, where gestures streamline processes and minimize hardware usage, thereby saving time. Additionally, it serves as an accessible communication interface for individuals with physical disabilities and the elderly. Moreover, it simplifies presentations, reducing the requirement for extra hardware and decluttering workspaces.

By replacing traditional hardware, this system brings users closer to their workspace, enhancing convenience and user experience. Its adaptability in education, accessibility features, and simplification of presentations underscore its potential to revolutionize computer interactions, making them more user-friendly and intuitive.

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